

AGENDA

GREENSCENT YOUTH ASSEMBLY IN-PERSON MEETING IN NOVI SAD, SERBIA

OCTOBER 6-8, 2023

FRIDAY 6TH

CHECK IN - 14.00-16.30

HOTEL VELIKI, NIKOLE PAŠIĆA 24, 21000 NOVI SAD, VOJVODINA

IF YOU ARRIVE BEFORE 14.00, THE HOTEL CAN OFFER YOU A PLACE WHERE YOU CAN STORE YOUR LUGGAGE SAFELY.

MEET-UP + WALK & TALK - 16.30-17.45

SOCIAL ACTIVITIES AND WALK & TALK ABOUT CIRCULAR ECONOMY

DAUNAUB PARK

SNACK BREAK - 17.45-18:00

GETTING STARTED: CIRCULAR ECONOMY - 17.45-18.30

INTRODUCTION TO THE AGENDA AND TO CIRCULAR ECONOMY

HOTEL VELIKI, NIKOLE PAŠIĆA 24, 21000 NOVI SAD, VOJVODINA

GETTING STARTED: CITIZEN JOURNALISM - 18.30-19.00

INTRODUCTION TO FARM TO FORK AND CITIZEN JOURNALISM IN GREENSCENT

HOTEL VELIKI, NIKOLE PAŠIĆA 24, 21000 NOVI SAD, VOJVODINA

FRIDAY 6TH

WALK TO THE RESTAURANT - 19.00-19.15

WE WALK TOGETHER TO THE RESTAURANT

DINNER AT “THE LOFT” - 20.00-22.00

NIEGOSEVA 2, NOVI SAD

WALK TO THE HOTEL- AFTER DINNER

DITTE AND MATTIAS WILL WALK BACK TO HOTEL VELIKI, NIKOLE PAŠIĆA
24, 21000 NOVI SAD, VOJVODINA

*MAKE SURE THAT YOU ARE READY FOR TOMORROW'S PROGRAM TOMORROW
AT 08:30 (BREAKFAST STARTS AT 08:00 AND WE LEAVE TOGETHER 08:30).*

SATURDAY 7TH

BREAKFAST IN THE HOTEL - 8.00-8.30

BREAKFAST AND GOOD MORNING IN THE HOTEL RESTAURANT
HOTEL VELIKI, NIKOLE PAŠIĆA 24, 21000 NOVI SAD, VOJVODINA

WALK TO THE FACULTY OF SCIENCES - 8.30 - 9.00

WE ARE LEAVING THE HOTEL FOR THE DAY, AND THE FIRST STOP IS THE FACULTY OF SCIENCES. WE WILL WALK TOGETHER.

IMPORTANT: REMEMBER TO WEAR PRACTICAL SHOES AND CLOTHES, AND BRING A BOTTLE OF WATER.

WELCOMING WORDS - 9.00-9.15

WELCOMING WORDS FROM OUR HOSTS AT THE FACULTY OF SCIENCE
FACULTY OF SCIENCES, TRG DOSITEJA OBRADOVIĆA 3, 21102 NOVI SAD

CIRCULAR ECONOMY - 09.15-10.15

LECTURE WITH PROFESSOR ĐURĐA KERKEZ
FACULTY OF SCIENCES, TRG DOSITEJA OBRADOVIĆA 3, 21102 NOVI SAD

WALK TO NS SEME - 10:15-10.30

WE WILL WALK TOGETHER, TALKING ABOUT THE LECTURE

VISIT TO NS SEME - 10:30-11.40

WE WILL VISIT NS SEME; THE INSTITUTE OF FIELD AND VEGETABLE CROPS
MAKSIMA GORKOG 30, 21101 NOVI SAD

BUS TO GRADSKO ZELENILO - 11:40-12.00

GRADSKO ZELENILO COMPOSTING SITE - 12:00-14.00

VISIT TO THE GREEN WASTE COMPOSTING SITE W/ PROF. ĐURĐA KERKEZ
MLADENA LESKOVCA 1, NOVI SAD, SERBIEN

SATURDAY 7TH

BUS TO CITY CENTER- 14.00-14.30

LUNCH AT MACCHIATO FAX - 14.30-15.30

WE WILL EAT SLICES OF SHARED PIZZAS AT MACCHIATO FAX
STEVANA MUSIĆA 20, NOVI SAD 21000

PRESENTATION FROM OIC WINNERS - 15.30-16:00

PRESENTATION FROM THE WINNERS OF THE OPEN INNOVATION CHALLENGE
FACULTY OF SCIENCES, TRG DOSITEJA OBRADOVIĆA 3, 21102 NOVI SAD

EVALUATING THE CITIZEN JOURNALISM TOOLS - 16.00-16.45

WE WILL USE THE GREENSCENT APP TO DOCUMENT OUR VISITS OF THE DAY AND START WRITING BLOG POSTS FOR THE GREENSCENT WEBSITE AND SO-ME.

CITY WALK: PETROVARADIN FORTRESS - 16.45-20.00

WE WILL WALK TO THE PETROVARADIN FORTRESS, EXPLORE THE FORTRESS ABOVE GROUND AND VISIT THE ART STUDIOS THERE

DINNER AT PETRUS CAFFE - 20.00-22.00

TRG SLOBODE 4, 21000 NOVI SAD

WALK TO THE HOTEL - AFTER DINNER

DITTE AND MATTIAS WILL WALK BACK TO HOTEL VELIKI,
NIKOLE PAŠIĆA 24, 21000 NOVI SAD, VOJVODINA

*MAKE SURE THAT YOU ARE READY FOR TOMORROW'S PROGRAM SUNDAY
BEGINNING AT 9.00 WITH CHECKOUT (BREAKFAST BETWEEN 8.00 AND 9.00)*

SUNDAY 8TH

BREAKFAST IN THE HOTEL - 8.00-9.15

GOODMORNING, BREAKFAST AND CHECK OUT AT THE HOTEL

EVERYBODY SHOULD HAVE CHECKED OUT BEFORE 9.15.

YOU CAN LEAVE YOUR LUGGAGE AT THE RECEPTION UNTIL YOUR DEPARTURE.

COMPETENCE WORKSHOP - 9.30 - 12.45

DURING THE WORKSHOP, WE WILL BE DISCUSSING AND PROVIDING FEEDBACK ON THE GREENSCENT COMPETENCE FRAMEWORK.

HOTEL VELIKI, NIKOLE PAŠIĆA 24, 21000 NOVI SAD, VOJVODINA

LUNCH AT THE HOTEL RESTAURANT - 12.45 - 13.45

FOLLOW UP AND FAMILY PHOTO - 13.45-14.00

HOTEL VELIKI, NIKOLE PAŠIĆA 24, 21000 NOVI SAD, VOJVODINA

GOODBYE AT THE HOTEL - 14:00

WE WILL PICK UP OUR BAGS AT THE HOTEL AND SAY GOODBYE